

ARCHITECT AMIR TEMUR PALACE GARDENS

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Abstract: The peoples of Central Asia have been paying attention to the construction of residential buildings since ancient times. This situation has intensified especially during the period of peace in the territory of the country. Including in the XIV-XV centuries, the construction of new buildings and gardens increased due to the period of the Timurid dynasty in our country. In the following article, we will present the construction architecture, history and other information of some of these parks. After all, they are also a part of history.

Key words: Samarkand, Claviho, Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi, Chorbog, Shikor, Bogi Dilkusho, Bogi Bihisht, Spain, Takti Karacha, Gulbog.

Sahibqiron Amir Temur, the founder of the Timurid dynasty and a high representative of creative activity, carried out creative works on a large scale during his time. We can see the incomparable works of the masters in the field of architectural creativity in the example of the unique and rare monuments that have been preserved until now in the cities of Shahrissabz, Samarkand, Bukhara, Tashkent, and Turkestan. During his time, Amir Temur gathered architects and engineers around him as "developers of the royal enterprise". About this, Sahibqiron says in his work "Temur Salts", "I built high-rise buildings in cooperation with engineers and drew the project outline of gardens."

In the historical documents of that time, one can find such names as: Khwaja Mahmud Davud, Muhammad Jald, Muhammad ibn Mahsud Isfahani, gardener Shihabuddin Ahmad Zardakashi, painter and painter Abdulhai Bagdadiyya, and architect Sheikh Muhammad Tabrizi. However, the names of some master artists have been forgotten¹.

In fact, there are such masters who lived in the region of Movorounnahr that even a person who does not know their life is amazed by their work. The creations of such masters, as well as the ruling class that gave them the opportunity, will remain in the memory of generations for years. One of such rulers is our grandfather Amir Temur. This person paid attention to building not only architectural monuments, but also gardens. The Spanish ambassador remembers this in his memoirs. According to him, he visits interesting parks located between Shahrissabz and Samarkand city and gives information about some parks that he was impressed by in his work. We will mention some of them below.

Bogi Jahannamo. It was near the present village of Karatepa, located 24 kilometers south of Samarkand. The palace is three-storeyed, and its walls are decorated with scenes from the wars led by Amir Temur. Sahibqiran also received ambassadors in Bogi Jahannamo. Historians of that time wrote about it in their works. Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi said the following about this magnificent garden: "A castle was ordered to be built on the kokhbora in the

¹ Usmanov B.A. Timurid and Shaibani period. Page 90

middle of the garden. After this commandment, which must be fulfilled, was executed and the castle was built, it was named "Takhti Karacha"². From this information, we can see that another name of the park is Takti Karacha. In a sense, it is natural that it is called by several names. The reason is that according to the situation of that time, various historians have described in their work taking into account the common names of the garden.

Gulbagh or Davlatabad. This garden was also built during the time of Amir Temur, and we can get more complete information about it from the memoirs of the Spanish ambassador. The reason for this is that the ambassadors who visited the Timurid Palace at that time stayed in Gulbog for several days and wrote about this beautiful garden in their books. We will quote their information below. "The garden was surrounded by a thatched wall, the circumference of the wall was equal to a full league (6 km). There were fruit trees in the garden. There were six ponds in it, and a canal flowed through the middle of the garden.

The ponds are connected to each other by a path formed by a row of tall, shady trees. This green corridor rose to the height, and the paths were sloping. There is a flat high hill in the garden, raised from the ground, surrounded by wooden fences. There is a magnificent castle.

The palace is perfectly polished with gold, lapis lazuli and colored tiles. This hill on which the castle is located is surrounded by a water-filled moat. Water flows continuously in the ditch. Two bridges were built on both sides of the palace on the hill

There are two doors on the other side of the bridges. After entering the door, he climbs the stairs to the hill."³

The remains of this garden have been preserved as an archeological monument on the banks of the Dargom River. In the image of the garden, the structure of many special gardens and the architectural appearance of the palace in the narrowest place are fully expressed in the period of Amir Temur.

In general, during the time of Amir Temur, the structure of the gardens had two forms:

The first are the chorbogs - geometric (rectangular) in shape, and each side extends to a distance of about 1 km.

The second one was built in the bosom of non-geometric gardens, natural trees and thickets. Such gardens are often intended for hunting.

Dilkusho garden. It is one of the most beautiful and majestic parks in Samarkand. Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi left very valuable information about this garden. "The roofs of the palace are decorated with ornamental and glazed bricks. Magnificent sheds were built with great skill and taste in the four corners of the garden. The garden was divided into lawns and flower gardens of different shapes.

Amir Temur wanted to plant fruit trees on the side of the avenues, and flowers on some of them. Amir Temur called it Bogi Dilkusho because the garden was worthy of his taste..."⁴

In the middle of the garden, a high three-pedestal palace was restored and it was decorated with beautiful patterns that amaze the human eye. The strong and durable construction of this garden, the variety of decorations are commendable⁵.

² Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi. Zafarnoma. / The author of the translation from Persian is Omonullo Boriyev. 1994

³ Clavijo. R.G. Diary of a trip to Samarkand-Amir Temur Palace. Translation by B. Ahmedov.

⁴ Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi. Zafarnoma. The creativity of the Timurids is in the sources of the period.

⁵ Usmanov B.A. Timurid and Shaibani period. Page 98

More specific information about Dilkusho garden and its location can be found only in Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's chronicle. According to him: "(Temurbek) built two gardens in the east of Samarkand, one of them is far away, Boldu Garden, and the more distant one is Dilkusho Garden. Andin made an avenue up to the Feruza gate and planted poplar trees on both sides. In Dilkusha, there is also a great painting, in which they depict Temurbek's Indian war."⁶

Garden of Paradise. It is a fortress built according to the order of Amir Temur. This park is located on the sunny side of Samarkand. Clavijo describes the landscape between this garden and the garden as "ultimately beautiful". "This garden has a tall and beautiful gate decorated with bricks and ornaments, gilt and gold. The garden is very big. It has a lot of fruit and shade trees. people pass through the alleys and corridors surrounded by wooden fences."⁷

In short, as much attention was paid to the construction of buildings during the Timurid period, no less attention was paid to the establishment of gardens. From this we can see the prosperity and stability of peace during the time of Amir Temur. Of course, in order to improve the country, it is necessary to establish peace in the country first. The presence of a certain system in the construction of gardens, the high taste in construction attracts the attention of many scientists to this day. The use of various ornaments in the decoration of the gardens, the samples of painting and calligraphy placed on the majestic and beautiful pillars will not fail to amaze anyone who has studied the history of our country. Like our history, our ancient monuments and gardens are magnificent. It is the duty of today's growing generation to further research them and pass them on to the next generation.

⁶ Babur.Z.M. Baburnama page 44

⁷ Clavijo. R.G. History of Timur the Great

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